

BAYVIEW TEES-OFF AT HUMEWOOD

Brendan Muldoon

The 6th green shows even quicker covering after five weeks.

Derryck le Roux, greens keeper for Humewood Golf Club, is thrilled with both of his recent discoveries. Last year, their greens committee decided to test Bayview on their 16th green after being impressed with its performance at the Walmer 8th Avenue Bowling Club.

Immediately after the 16th was re-opened for play, favourable comments were made. The shorter nap of

Bayview compared to the local kwek makes the green faster. So good was this green, that the general consensus after the 1987 Goodyear Classic was that the Humewood 16th has the best putting surface of any green on the coastal courses.

The performance of Bayview on the 4th green (replanted in October 1987) was so good that the Club decided to replant the remaining 16 greens to Bayview. At this stage, the concept of replanting using Bayview plugs produced in Speedling trays was introduced to Derryck. An extremely limited trial resulted in an immediate commission to Rob Malan of Saturn Seedlings to produce the required number of plugs.

Greens were prepared for replanting by deep scarifying followed by hollow tining. The original grass was poisoned by methyl bromide fumigation with the roots left in the soil for extra stabilization. The Speedling plugs were air-freighted from Pretoria and transplanted to a 25 cm grid pattern. A light roller was used to firm them in, followed by irrigation.

Transplanting with Speedling plugs proved to be two to three times quicker than with runners. The cost of the planting material — including air

Runners and plugs transplanted next to each other.

freighting — ended up about 25% of estimated costs for runners. The 100% take and complete elimination of transplant shock has resulted in an 80–90% cover six weeks after transplanting. Reopening of the greens is expected to be 45 days earlier than previously estimated.

The minimal soil disturbance during plug transplanting meant that less topsoil has been required to level the greens. An important factor at this windy site has been the drastically reduced effects of wind erosion.

The Speedling technique can also be used for plugging into gaps caused by excessive wear in patches. The quick regrowth soon masks any sign of wear and patchiness without requiring major renovation and disruption of the green.

Derryck le Roux checking the 18th green five weeks from transplanting. The bare patch behind him had to be replanted where spot fumigation was required after transplanting.

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Trace elements are essential!

Dr Chris Dickens

The growing of seedlings in South Africa has undergone a revolution since the introduction of composted bark mixes. These mixes are most suited to seedling growth, as they allow good drainage and aeration.

Provided that adequate water is provided, plants have every opportunity to grow abundant roots and healthy shoots. High leaching conditions results in a requirement for regular, small quantities of nutrients. Occasional large quantities are not suitable since the nutrients are not retained for long in the bark medium. This has led to the situation where most seedlings are fed by fertigation, a process not far removed from hydroponics.

Fertilizer is applied with every watering, in very dilute concentrations. The three major elements (N, P and K) are routinely applied but trace elements are often neglected. This can be a dangerous mistake, as trace elements, although required in small concentrations, are vital for plant growth and can have a bigger effect than the application of N, P or K.

Increases in growth of up to 800% have been recorded, while deficiencies in any one of the elements can lead to growth retardation of more than 80%.

The easiest way to ensure an adequate supply of trace elements is to provide the plants with low concentrations of all six elements. Trelmix Trace Element Solution has been formulated so that all the trace elements are in the concentrations most suited for plant growth. The continual application of dilutions between 1:3000 and 1:6000 removes any chance of deficiency symptoms occurring. An alternative is to apply trace elements by adding Trelmix at a higher concentration in weekly doses.

Although it is best to apply Trelmix alone or with a balanced fertilizer, it is compatible with most pesticides. Any such mixture should be tested before using, by adding the two diluted products together in a glass vessel and looking for any precipitate which may form.

The most important point to remember, is not to forget to supply trace elements. Your plants need them.

The Humewood 10th green showing rapid cover where plugs were transplanted five weeks previously.

BAYVIEW

A wild *Cynodon dactylon* growing near Somerset West overlooking False Bay was collected and selected for hardiness, vigour and persistence at the Starke Ayres experimental farm in the Klein Karoo. Ned Kerr, then Technical Director of Starke Ayres, supervised this selection process. The result is an extremely hardy, vigorous, wear-resistant and very fine textured grass.

Bayview can withstand light frost and is used for all types of greens, cricket wickets and domestic lawns.

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ZINC:	Sugar and hormone production, cell division and

thus all growth, pollination and fertilization, (vital for fruit crops such as citrus).

Many soils are deficient in these elements, especially where intensive cultivation has taken place.

Sterile bark media are particularly deficient in these elements, and even when added, are rapidly washed through during watering. Repeated applications of TRELMIX Trace Elements as well as normal fertilizers are essential for healthy growth.

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MULTI-SEEDED ONION PLUGS

LOCAL RESEARCH PROVES FEASIBILITY

Dr. I. Smith, Dept Hort. Science, University of Natal, Pietermaritzburg

Multi-seeded onion plugs are a new concept to most South African farmers. The benefits of transplanted seedlings over direct sown onions is the better control over seed germination and therefore plant population, a reduction in water requirements and reduced time in the field with all that that entails.

Traditional transplants are pencil-thickness seedlings which have been topped in the seedbed. Multi-seeded plugs are easier and quicker to transplant and result in greater yield uniformity. Since this system is new to South Africa, controlled trials were required to determine optimum number of seedlings per plug combined with optimum plant population in the field. This was conducted at the Ukulinga Research Station of the University of Natal near Pietermaritzburg during 1987.

The trial used the cultivar Pyramid and tested the performance of a range of seedling numbers per plug in different plug sizes and at a range of final field plant populations. The results obtained largely followed what is already known to affect bulb size, splitting and bolting as well as confirming most of the current recommendations for using the multi-seeded onion plug system, as reported from the UK.

Bolting (formation of a flower stalk) was more prevalent at higher field plant populations but was decreased by a larger number of seedlings per plug as well as a smaller size plug. This agrees with the known principle that transplanting smaller seedlings results

in less bolting. Bulb splitting followed the same trends as bolting and was related to seedling size at time of transplanting.

Bulb size was strongly correlated with field plant population. Bulbs tend to be smaller as the number of bulbs increased. There was no apparent correlation between bulb size and number of seedlings per plug. Total yield increased with an increase in plant population, but the percentage of small bulbs increased similarly.

Bulb shape was a major concern as the clusters of bulbs were thought to induce wedge shapes. Although this appeared to be the case during the early stages of bulb filling, the effect disappeared at maturity.

The results of this trial suggested that an optimum of seven seedlings per model 200 plug with a field population of about 750 000 plants per hectare (107 142 plugs per hectare) were required to obtain the best benefit from a maximum proportion of medium sized bulbs. This plant population requires a plug spacing of about 45 x 20 cm between and within rows. Multiple seeding reduces the cost of the plug system to acceptable levels in comparison with normal seedbed grown seedlings. ▼

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In fewer than nine years from the first trials, the Speedling system is used for nearly half of all forest seedlings.

The reasons for this massive change are numerous. However, economy of resources and the possibility of obtaining seedlings which are easy to transport, handle and plant are probably most important. Coupled with this swing towards Speedling has been the rapid proliferation of commercial nurseries. This has freed the plantation staff from the unwelcome task of caring for numerous small seedling nurseries.

With the change towards buying commercially grown seedlings has come the awareness of the similarities in growing seedlings of widely varying types. Where previously the differences were emphasised, now the same

nurseryman is growing forestry, vegetable, flower, pasture and landscape seedlings.

As with any viable nursery, innovations are inevitable and essential. Increased nursery efficiency, improved seedling quality and reduced field mortality are the main areas of innovation.

Larger seedlings generally preferred by plantation staff cause a direct conflict for nurserymen who must limit seedling size to make maximum use of available nursery space. This conflict has already resulted in many seed-related innovations to improve the percentage of occupied cells, even to the extent of sowing pregerminated seed.

Since very young seedlings require

little space, a further innovation, practised by Speedling Incorporated, U.S.A., is to sow into small celled trays and transplant to the larger cells at a later stage. Not only does this optimise nursery space utilization by allocating a smaller area for small seedlings and ensuring a 100% stand of the larger seedlings, but the root pruning at different stages gives a more fibrous root system.

Gapping up and thinning of seedlings is eliminated, a practise considered to increase the incidence of Jay rooting. A quality check at the transplanting stage would also ensure a far higher degree of uniformity at time of field planting.

With greater investments in modern forestry, it would be unwise to plant inferior quality seedlings. ▼

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A Plug for the Speedling-Transplant

One of the most important activities carried out at Speedling Inc., Florida, is the transplanting of seedlings from the small cells of the germination tray into the larger celled growing on trays. This type of activity is conspicuous by its absence from South African nurseries.

Speedling-transplanting can benefit the nurseryman and the final customer enormously. By spending the first part of its life in the small cells, the seedling takes up less nursery space, requires less medium and fertilizer. When the seedlings are Speedling-transplanted into the larger cells, a 100% stand is feasible. This ensures that no valuable nursery space is wasted. At the same time, seedlings can be graded for uniformity. A major benefit to using Speedling is the uniformity which can be maintained right through to harvest.

The main types of seedlings where this Speedling-transplant system would prove particularly useful are tobacco, forestry and flowers. Having the root system induced into the fibrous form by air-pruning in the smaller cells helps form a dense root plug in the larger cells.

A further extension of this method would be for the end user to purchase the initial transplants from a nursery and grow them on to field size in a less sophisticated facility. The larger-sized transplants favoured for field transplanting would be easier to manage in the typical farm facility. Not only is overall management less critical with larger size cells, but improved field performance is often noted.

How can this method reduce costs when more uniform, better quality seedlings are the end result? Optimisation of resources is the answer. Young seedlings do not require much space, therefore using the Model 338 means that an 80% seed germination wastes 192 ml of medium and 176 cm² of nursery bench space compared to 992 ml and 465 cm² if sown into a Model 128 tray. Since the final tray capacity would be fully utilized by usable seedlings, changing to Model 98 trays at this stage would represent the equivalent of a 76,5% stand in Model 128 trays.

Machine sowing of seed is becoming more common. Optimising the capital expended on the machinery by fully utilizing its capacity is sound business sense. Good germination facilities are a feature of a good nursery. Much simpler 'growing on' nurseries are required at later stages of seedling growth. In many instances, this can be done on the farm. ▼

PLUG PARALLELS — U.S. PREDICTIONS

Towards the end of 1986, a National Plug Production Conference was held at the Iowa State University. Dr. Louis Berninger (Speedling Inc., Sun City) made some interesting predictions.

While the current trend is towards smaller cells (more than 600 cells per tray) with some growers, the demands of a quick turnover require larger sized plugs.

He notes that most nurseries will use poppers to dislodge seedlings from trays and to reduce losses in damaged plants.

Sales of seedlings are likely to become direct to the customer (our local industry has grown using this method).

Of particular interest to South African nurserymen is the movement of the U.S. industry towards a mature state with fewer new nurseries breaking into the industry with price incentives.

Our own seedling industry is showing a combination of rapid growth in some areas with aspects of a mature industry elsewhere. ▼

Mechanisation in the nursery — here is a machine which washes trays and treats them with Styrodip.

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Don't Keep Off The Grass!

The concept of using Speedling to establish K11 pastures has been tested since 1984. After initial enthusiasm, the concept took a back seat until Dave Biggs of Sutherland Seedlings took it up again. Although initially growing only K11 for his dairy farmer customers, Dave has since found considerable demand for many other grasses.

Only creeping types of grass have been used. For pasture requirements using the Coast Cross strains such as K11 and Tifton 78, experience indicates a planting density of 10 000 per hectare to be adequate. It is not uncommon for cattle to be taking their first grazing only six weeks from transplanting.

The speed of establishment of pastures from plugs can mean a tremendous saving to farmers. The spread of runners from the plugs soon gives a full cover resulting in a greatly reduced weed control programme. Since much less runner material is required to plant up a pasture via Speedling, a saving in establishment costs can be realized as well as a far greater degree of purity.

Dave has also found that farmers are now asking for plugs of pasture grasses which were traditionally sown directly. Kikuyu seedlings have been most in demand. A further development has been a requirement

K11 Speedling plug ready for transplant.

for lawn grasses.

For lawns, a planting rate of 9-18 plugs per square metre is recommended. Closer spacing will give a quicker cover but a higher cost. Speedling is expected to give bowling and golf clubs a boost in planting up new grass or for renovating older greens. The plugs are more vigorous than runners and are easier to transplant.

For road-side grassing and general landscaping purposes, particularly on steep banks, using Speedling grass plugs is quicker than direct sowing and more convenient than ready grown turf. The range of grasses suitable for

general landscaping is much more varied. Both seed and runners can be used to grow plugs. This is only one application where Speedling can be used in landscaping.

Rapid growth and low mortality are major factors in choosing the Speedling system for grass establishment. Purity and stretching of low reserves of vegetative propagation material as well as considerable cost benefits are further advantages. Establishment of grass, whether pasture, bowling green, household lawns or road verges, via the Speedling system has become a preferred alternative.

Early Crops

Early sweetcorn or green mealies are often started in Speedling trays. By keeping plants in a plastic tunnel, problems with late frost, poor early growth and erratic germination are overcome.

An early butternut crop off to a good start.

Much the same advantage is obtained with early melons and similar crops. As the improved hybrid varieties become better known, the trend is towards starting even main season crops in Speedling rather than direct seeding.

Earliness in crops is typically dependant on soil temperatures and the incidence of late frosts. By using the Speedling route, soil temperature effects are largely overcome. The ease of moving seedlings large distances also gives the farmer looking for an early crop the option of having seedlings grown at a nursery in a warmer region.

Veld Upgrading and Regeneration with

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Warrick Nelson

The introduction of desirable forage species into eroded veld can be achieved by plugging the gaps with grass and legume seedlings. This method for pasture establishment has been well tested using Kikuyu and similar grass types.

Stooling and tufty grasses are unlikely to lend themselves to pasture establishment in competition with direct seeding methods. However, where establishment is necessary in harsh conditions, the use of grass plugs will be called for.

Bare patches between areas of adequate grass cover cannot easily be established from seed. However, a few grass plugs at 20 to 30 cm spacing can overcome the problem. Only spot ground preparation is required and can be done immediately prior to transplanting.

Donga reclamation and stabilisation using runner grasses or *Eragrostis curvula* is another application for Speedling plugs. Poor soil structure

and the difficulty of adequate soil preparation mean seed germination and emergence is erratic in dongas. Plugs are quicker to establish and are therefore less vulnerable to washing out, as well as being more amenable to dry season transplanting.

Upgrading of existing pastures by plugging in suitable legumes is a further possibility. Successful inoculation and nodulation in the nursery is easily checked before sending plants out. Silver and green leaved *Desmodium*, lucernes and clovers could be added using this technique.

Successful establishment requires the root plug to be thoroughly saturated before transplanting and spot watering to settle the soil around the roots is advisable. With this rapid growth potential, upgrading of old veld and revegetation of eroded lands can be considerably speeded up by using pasture seedling plugs in the Speedling system.

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WATTLE IT BE THIS TIME?

Warrick Nelson

Over the years, wattle seedlings have periodically caused headaches to nurserymen and their suppliers. Usually thought to be linked to wet conditions, the often massive seedling mortality was thought to be related to changes in growing medium properties and waterlogging conditions. In attempting to correct the drainage situation, a growing medium with fewer fine particles is produced for wattle seedlings.

This past summer season has been exceptionally cool and wet in the wattle growing regions. In spite of all attempts to maintain a quality growing medium, wattle seedling mortality has been widely experienced. On closer inspection, reddish brown lesions may be noted on seedling stems. These lesions girdle the stem and constrict it to the extent that it dies. If the lesions occur on the main stem, seedlings die, apparently of "damping off". Lesions on leaves are a brick red/brown colour and leaf drop is common.

The Department of Plant Pathology (University of Natal, Pietermaritzburg campus) first isolated fungal spores on seedlings from Top Crop Nursery.

Further investigations at other nurseries also experiencing leaf drop and seedling mortality in wattles has resulted in the same fungal infection.

Anthrachnose caused by *Colletotrichum* sp. is the result of these investigations. The disease is favoured by cool, damp conditions and is spread in the nursery by water splashes. Regions of disease tend to develop around a single diseased plant and gradually spread out across the nursery. While germination and early seedling growth are apparently unaffected, the disease can occur at any other stage while in the nursery.

Spread of the disease from seedling to seedling is relatively slow. Whether the disease is endemic in wattle growing regions or not is unknown. It is also not known where the disease is harboured during drier periods when wattle seedlings are not affected. The effect of moving infected seedlings to the field will require monitoring, but disease symptoms after transplanting have not been noted.

Now that a better understanding of the cause of wattle seedling decline is known, control measures can be

implemented. No chemical remedies have been registered for anthracnose control in wattle. Nurserymen should obtain further information from their nursery or forestry adviser. The Institute for Commercial Forestry Research may also be contacted for updated information. ▼

INSTANT FORESTRY?

John Jimbo of Gamadoela Nursery faces Monday morning with a smile. The 500 000 gum seedlings ordered by Successful Forestry are on schedule. They are in tip top condition and not only are they to be delivered on due date, but the weather forecast is a week of cool, drizzly weather.

As John returns to his nursery office after inspecting the final batch of seedlings, he is summoned to the telephone. Peter Piper is after forestry seedlings.

"Hello John, superb transplanting weather, isn't it?"

"Yup, it sure is."

"D'you remember that site across from the dam where I've had beef cattle? I've been thinking for some time that with all this wood shortage and things, maybe I should put some trees there. A fellow at the pub was saying how much we'll be paid for wood if we plant now."

"Yes, Peter, I know that site, I've wondered for some time why you didn't put it under timber."

"Well, I was wondering if I could send my bakkie round so we can plant out in this weather."

"Sorry, Peter, I've just sent off an order and all the other seedlings I've got are for orders. Besides, they're not ready to go out just yet."

"Ag John, surely you must have a few thousand spare. You must have millions of seedlings there."

"Well, we are busy cleaning out the Speedling trays from this mornings order and we do throw away a lot, but they are the runts and I couldn't sell them to you. They wouldn't grow properly, that's why we throw them out."

"Those sound O.K. to me. I want to start planting this afternoon, and if you were going to throw them away, you might as well give them to me — or at least at a good price!"

In the end, Peter collects a few thousand seedlings which should not have been planted out. The site they went to had not been prepared and the species was not suited to the local

climate. Consequently, after one year, John hears in the pub that his seedlings are no good; they can't take being planted out in spite of the ideal planting weather!

Is this an extreme example? Perhaps, but remember that forestry seedlings typically require 3–4 months for hardwood and 5–6 months for softwood species. Do plan your operation so that site preparation occurs in time for the seedlings which were ordered well in advance. Do get good advice as to the species to plant and plan in advance where that timber will be sold in ten or more years time.

The local pub is probably not the best place to obtain information to help in planning your afforestation programme. The Directorate of Forestry, the Institute for Commercial Forestry Research, timber companies and forest seedling suppliers are sources of information to help your timber planning.

Use their experience to your advantage! ▼

Extravaganza Symposium!

Sun City, Bophuthatswana, was the venue for the 4th National Symposium. The Seedling Growers Association put together an impressive programme involving not only aspects of seedling production, but involving many interesting factors which affect plants after the nursery stage.

Multi-seeded onions and tobacco were specifically highlighted as they are expected to have a major impact on the seedling industry. Dr. Bob Hiron, Deputy Director of Kirton Horticultural Experiment Station had some very pertinent comments. Although he does not claim to have originated the concept of multi-seeded onion plugs, his research work on this crop has resulted in many U.K. growers achieving far better harvests than is possible using traditional methods of propagation. This technique results in reliable high yields with greater chances to manipulate the size grade harvested.

Hannes Blignaut, an extension officer with the Laeveld Tabakkoöperasie raised eyebrows when he noted that 150 million tobacco seedlings are used annually in the Transvaal. The cooperatives own research programme clearly shows the value of using Speedling seedlings compared to the traditional seedbed seedlings. Since a

Bob and Linda Hiron inspecting seedlings while Bryan and Dave look on.

good seedling is the foundation of any crop, quality in the nursery is imperative. Uniformity of seedlings is a major factor in obtaining uniformity in the land. This allows for a higher grade of leaf harvested and delivered for processing. With the current

price/grade interaction, it pays to produce the highest quality tobacco. This is where Speedling can help the industry.

The session on nutrition was particularly enlightening. The differences in growing techniques and nutritional requirements of peat and bark-based growing media were clearly explained. Optimum control of seedling growth through fertilizer manipulation requires control of leaching and close monitoring of the nutritional status of the growing medium.

Guayule is potentially a good crop to establish through the Speedling system. This desert shrub is a source of good quality natural rubber and is showing potential for production in South Africa. The general shortage of quality seed makes an efficient propagation system imperative.

This 4th National Symposium is concrete evidence of a thriving seedling industry and congratulations to the Seedling Growers Association. We look forward to a year of further leaps in our understanding of seedling production.

No firm evidence has come to light to confirm that a lucky nurseryman hit the jackpot on the fruit machines and received a payout of 10 000 cabbage seedlings!

Gus Kohne, Irwin Smith and Bob Hiron at the Symposium.

American leafminer is becoming a serious threat to vegetable production in certain regions. Tomatoes are a favourite host, although a very wide range of crops is attacked. Nurserymen need to take particular care to control leafminer in the nursery. Here are the trails of the leafminer on a cabbage seedling.

Sweet Success with Setts

Sugar cane multiplied as single-eye setts is gaining a place in the sugar industry. These transplants are proving useful in a number of diverse situations.

The capacity for rapid multiplication of new varieties from a small quantity of original material will increase the rate of change to improved varieties by the industry. The better control of varietal purity and ease of transport of transplants are added advantages.

Every now and then, farmers require to replant certain lands which are

inaccessible to large trucks. The small weight of transplants compared to conventional seed cane means that transport problems are greatly reduced. This is particularly true of replanting in very wet weather when road conditions have deteriorated.

Minimum tillage requirements or other reasons preventing adequate land preparation are not a problem for transplants. They are easily transplanted into holes prepared as required. This system reduces labour

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and machinery requirements as well as reducing the hazard of erosion.

The major usage of cane transplants will most likely be for the establishment of seed cane nurseries. Transplants are another tool in the control of pest and disease spread as well as upgrading existing plantations by ensuring varietal purity. ▼

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SEEDLINGS SAAILINGE

Donga Reclamation

Eroded lands are normally difficult to revegetate since their surface soils are normally the subsoil horizons. In these difficult sites, grass plugs are likely to be difficult to establish, particularly as normal soil preparation methods are virtually impossible.

Choose larger sized grass plugs (Model 72 or 98) and apply a small quantity of superphosphate into each planting hole beneath the plug. Ensure that the plugs are saturated, preferably with a nutrient solution.

Always transplant plugs with the surface of the plugs slightly below the surrounding soil surface. This will prevent evaporation at the plug surface and the creation of a wick effect drawing out soil moisture. ▼

OBITUARY

Aubrey John Mullins, B.Sc. M.Sc.

It is with the deepest regret that we learned of the sudden death of Aubrey Mullins on Friday 11th March.

Aubrey took his primary degree in Horticulture at Natal University and subsequently his masters' degree at Stellenbosch University where he specialised in deciduous fruit. He joined the Department of Agriculture and for the major part of his working life was associated with the Fruit Research Institute in Stellenbosch.

During that period he was associated with the late Allen Starke, Technical Director of Starke Ayres, in promoting the concept of plant improvement in nursery stock through the formation of an association of breeders and propagators dedicated to this end. The organisation was known as Plantas.

Apart from a short period at Rooodeplaas Horticultural Research Institute near Pretoria, Aubrey had been a popular lecturer in horticulture at Cedara Agricultural College for the past five years. He had a particular interest in the economics and marketing of horticultural crops.

Aubrey Mullins was a gentleman in every sense of the word, beloved by his friends and was never known to speak a harsh word about anyone.

The staff of Starke Ayres wishes to convey its deepest sympathy to the Mullins family in its bereavement.

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Company/Maatskappy

Code/Kode

Business e.g. — forestry, vegetable farmer, seedling grower etc.
Besigheid bv. — bosbou, groenteboer, saailing kweker ens.

EDITOR'S VIEW

The recent flooding of large tracts of South Africa has devastated much of previously arable land. However, apart from the direct damage, the markedly reduced growth of all crops in the unusually lengthy overcast conditions is a further setback. Most nurseries have had waterlogging and leaching factors affecting their seedling quality, while the erratic availability of transport has played havoc in bringing in trays and growing medium as well as shipping out of mature seedlings to farmers.

The Seedling Growers Association has had a very active year. The National Transplant Day was well attended by farmers and served as a meeting place between nurserymen and their customers. Later on, a

farmers' day specifically looking at the prospects for tobacco seedlings was held in the Transvaal Lowveld. These public relations activities are an excellent opportunity for interested farmers to learn more about how to get the most from their seedlings.

The 4th National Symposium was a forum for guest speakers to share their technical expertise with nurserymen. This function alone would justify the Association. Combined with the public relations and product development activities of the Association, a powerful organ exists to promote better agriculture in South Africa.

Attempts at veld and pasture improvement have been dealt a severe blow by climatic conditions over the past six months. All the more reason to increase activities towards more productive veld and pasture.

Landscapers have been largely left out of the picture concerning the new nursery techniques. The possibilities of grass plugs are dealt with in this issue, and articles concerning other aspects of landscape plant establishment are planned for in future issues. With the high value of professional landscaping, dead and dying plants simply cannot be tolerated. ▼

Seedling News

The cost of duplication of articles in English and Afrikaans is prohibitive. However, any readers requiring a specific article translated are welcome to request a typescript copy. Please include a self-addressed stamped envelope with your request and specify the desired article clearly.

Die kostes verbonde aan die plasing van artikels in beide Engels en Afrikaans is ontsaglik duur. Lesers wat 'n vertaling van enige artikel benodig is egter welkom om daarvoor aan te vra. Stuur 'n self-geadresseerde koevert met die nodige posseël aan ons en dui duidelik aan watter artikel u benodig. ▼

Seedling News

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Kwaliteitbeheer oor Groente-saad

Dit is alom bekend dat groentesaad uiters gevoelig is vir die toestande waaronder dit opgeberg word. Faktore soos humiditeit en temperatuur is veral van groot belang en kan die lewe van groentesaad baie benadeel.

Omdat Starke Ayres groentesaad in al vier die provinsies van die Republiek en Suidwes versprei, is 'n streng kontrolestelsel nodig om die kwaliteit van die saad te verseker. Om dié rede word alle saad twee maal per jaar

Jacobsen tafel gebruik vir ontkiemingstoetse.

EASY RIDER

Easy Rider — die nuutste byvoegsel aan ons reeks van gehalte **baster** spanspekke.

Die vrug van **Easy Rider** is effens ovaal met 'n growwe net en 'n gemiddelde massa van 1 kg. Die hoër suikerinhoud gee die vleis 'n uitstekende smaak wat, tesame met die goeie vervoer eienskappe, maak dit ideaal vir **uitvoer** asook vir die plaaslike **varsmerk**. Vir lang afstand vervoer moet die vrug goeies word wanneer die skil onder die net nog groen is. Die kultivar is verdraagsaam teenoor Fusarium ras 2, Poeieragtige skimmel, Slaprank en Swawelbrand.

KOOP MET VERTROUE

PRESTASIE BEPROEFDE SAAD

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getoets by die firma se saadtoetslaboratorium, Liesbeek, in Epping, Kaapstad.

Die laboratorium beskik oor die dienste van volledig opgeleide tegnisi. Hierdie personeel het die kursusse in saadtegnologie bygewoon en is dus ten volle gekwalifiseer om alle groentesaad te toets. Hulle behoort ook aan die Vereniging van Saadanaliste. Dié vereniging het ten doel die handhawing van hoë saadtoetsstandaarde. Deur gereelde byeenkomste waar probleem gevalle bespreek word, word verseker dat elke lid ingelig word oor die jongste ontwikkeling op die gebied van saadtoetsing. Saad toetse word dus uitgevoer in ooreenstemming met internasionale standaarde soos neergelê deur die Internasionale Saadtoets Assosiasie.

Die Liesbeek saadtoetslaboratorium was op 11 Junie 1984 geregistreer as volwaardige saadtoetslaboratorium. Om die registrasie te behou, moet die laboratorium voortdurend deelneem aan proeftoetse wat deur die Departement uitgestuur word. Die doel van die toetse is om te verseker dat die standaard van die toetse wat deur die laboratorium uitgevoer word, aan vereistes voldoen.

Elke saadlot word van 'n verwysingsnommer voorsien voordat dit oor die land versprei word. 'n Monster van elke saadlot by elk van die firma se vyf takke word getrek. Indien daar gevind word dat die ontkieming van 'n sekere saadlot afgeneem het, word alle tegniese personeel en verteenwoordigers daarvan in kennis gestel en word die saadlot uit die handel onttrek en vernietig.

Die metode is omslagtig en in sommige gevalle redelik duur, maar op hierdie manier maak Starke Ayres seker dat net die saad van goeie gehalte by die verbruiker uitkom. ▼